

THE ROLE OF MANAGERS IN ENSURING SOCIAL STABILITY

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Abstract. *This article deals with the issue of the role and place of leading personnel with the stability of social life, as a representative of the state of developed countries. Considering that the representatives of the state -leading cadres performing strategic and tactical tasks face society and the state. This means that an intellectual leader must face modern requirements and a sense of duty to states and society, and also, a real leader must meet modern requirements with the quality of personality, high morality and moral, spiritual, quality of the personality of modern leading cadres and those or me of states.*

Keywords: *spirituality educational work, important activity of the leader, social life and culture, spirituality cadres and leader.*

Currently, in ensuring the stability of social life in the countries of the world, there are differences between geopolitical and geo-economic resources. Rapidly developing information technologies by the XXI century have led to new qualitative changes in all spheres of social life of the world community, in particular, in the field of management. The rapid growth of social life requires the development of a strategy that provides an effective mechanism for solving the personnel issue with modern management skills on the scale of each country. First of all, a manager who is trusted by the state must organize activities in accordance with the current period. In this sense, the analysis of modern international management strategies, a clearer understanding of management, and the definition of long-term prospects for improving the effectiveness of their activities in order to determine the scientific and practical need for research has been challenged.

In developing countries, it is well known that management personnel are fully aware and, especially, gradually become aware of modern management innovations and participate in professional development. They attach particular importance to test practice in the developed countries of the world "USA, Japan and Western countries " [1]. This form of governance remains an important factor in creating and strengthening a positive image in the world community, determining its place and strengthening its integration. In the research of the world's leading research centers, special attention is paid to the development of an effective system of leadership in public administration, risk assessment in the spheres of socio-political life.

If you look at history, the leading staff is a representative of the state-a person who directly fulfills the strategic tasks set for us in any country. There are many people who want to get this great career, respect, but this duty and right is entrusted to only one person in each organization. This creates the need to choose the honest, enterprising, selfless, skilled, patriotic, and most knowledgeable of the leadership candidates. Every state in the world is struggling with the problem of improving the efficiency of its management. This situation is widely discussed by specialists in various industries. Especially economists in this area (F. Taylor, A. Fayol, M. Mescon, V. R. Vesnin, O. S. Vihansky, I. N. Gerchikova, etc.) in the research center, the main

attention is paid to the factors that affect business activity, proper organization of work in the workplace, rational distribution of tasks in the production process, improving the efficiency of production and financial indicators. Some psychologists(G. Becker, M. Olson, B. Skinner, V. M. Bekhterev, A. L. Zhuravlev, E. S. Kuzmin, A. N. Leontiev, etc.) on the organization of an effective management process if necessary, analyze the mechanism of interaction of several groups in the workplace with each other, strategies for behavior in processes, taking into account socio-psychological conditions, focusing on each personnel activity in the management system. On this issue, according to the recognition of sociologists (M. Weber, N. Smelzer, J. Homans, V. I. Bashmakov, V. I. Gerchikov, A. I. Kravchenko, J. T. Tishchenko, V. N. Shalenko, V. V. Sherbina and etc.) the implementing subject of management research should be processes that the goal-the labor market, management functions, the organization's project, types of organization, human resources, personnel management, etc. [2].

It is important to identify common problems in management, improve the effectiveness of management in the organization and focus on describing some aspects of management in solving problems there are the following: for example, organizational skills (G. Amelburg, T. V Peter, S. S. Frolov, S. V. Shekshnya, etc.), vertical conflict (J. I. lang, V. L. Dobraev, S. I. Erina, E. S. Kuzmin, etc.), motivation (D. McClelland, A. Maslow, F. Hersberg, A.V. Sergeichuk, etc.), organizational culture (R. Moran, R. Waterman, F. Harris, E. Shane, A. E. brakov, and others), the influence of gender equality behavior among subordinates(E. I. Komarov, O. N. Krichevskaya, G.V. Turevskaya, A. E. Chirikova, A. G. Steinberg) say about the importance of learning. In addition, several dozen of scientific studies have been conducted concerning the “The ideal manager”, innate abilities, behavioral (behavioral) character, horizontal and vertical conflict situations, stimulating criteria, service and management activities, and attempts are being made to create such a principle. However, after studying the identified problems, as a manager, despite a comprehensive review of the concept of leadership style, no empirical interpretation was found, the indicators of skills that allow him to work remain unclear. A much expanded study of these factors leads some researchers to go beyond it in their research.

The state policy of Uzbekistan pays special attention to the strategic directions of management. President of our country Shavkat Mirziyoyev put forward the main idea “From national revival to national progress”, which is contained in the Strategy of action for the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021. According to Jay Barney: "A strategy is a resource positioning model that builds on strengths and strengthens weaknesses, resulting in improved overall performance" [3]. Therefore, analyzing the consistent progress of our country on the path of sustainable development, we have every reason to say that over the past years, decisive steps have been taken to implement fundamentally important reforms.

At the same time, the action strategy is an important document for managing managerial personnel, which is relevant for ongoing changes in the system of public administration and scientific research. The reputation of the country, manhood, dedication in its interests, indefatigability in all links, in all links, is led by a humane, educated, experienced leader. This opinion in the Message of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis fully reflects the fact that “Each of us must once again realize that we are a people with a great history, a great culture, who are not afraid of any trials and overcome any difficulties on the way to a free and prosperous life with honor. If we work together, United and

conscientiously, we will be able to conquer the highest frontiers, open a new glorious page in the history of our people.” [4].

Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 PD-4947 “On a strategy for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan”, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan from September 8, 2017 PD -5185 “On approval of the concept of administrative reform in the Republic of Uzbekistan”, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Oliy Majlis and the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On openness of activities of state authorities and management”. This research work to a certain extent is the implementation of the tasks, defined by the laws “On social partnership ” and "On public control", as well as other regulatory legal acts related to the sphere.

We know from history that in our past there were enough scientists-physicists who theoretically justified the foundations of the great state. Because, as Abu Nasr Forobiy writes, one of the advantages of leadership is that it says: "The power to use them (subordinates) effectively, giving everyone a decent task depending on their talent and qualifications.” The thinker assumes that in his place will continue the constant pursuit of leadership and education, and that "Education and purification of the spirit will necessarily continue, and good deeds can be achieved![5], he stated.

In a comprehensive understanding of the great and unique mindset of Amir Temur, studying the political, socio-economic, spiritual and ideological foundations of the powerful Kingdom built by him, his huge potential, skill, knowledge and experience in the field of public administration of Sahibkiran, in General, in understanding the secrets of life, “The Code of Temui” serves as an invaluable guide. It is known that Amir Temur ruled the state on the principle of “power – justice”. It has organized management in accordance with the following 12 rules:

First, be based on the values that exist in their time.

Second, the management of society as a social category.

Third, there is advice in every job.

Fourth, obey only the laws in management.

Fifth, the promotion of civil servants.

The sixth is the consent of citizens.

Seventh-respect the people's dear people.

Eighth, work with enthusiasm.

Ninth - always be aware of the situation of the citizen.

Tenth-to appreciate active people in the service.

The eleventh, not forgetting the service of good people.

The twelfth - to establish the supply of the army at the necessary level.

These are the principles of justice that Emir Temur applied in his administration. Their essence is only in the interests of the person. The great Sahibkiran Amir Temur notes that "If the state is not created on the basis of law, the glory, power and order of such a Kingdom will disappear" [6]. It is noteworthy that in the rule of Amir Temur and the former Soviet totalitarian States, there is a difference between the Earth and the sky. When Amir Temur chose justice as the main slogan, selfishness and decency were highly valued in many of the management ideologies of former Soviet leaders. In this sense, the element of justice in the idea of guiding spirituality is justice, knowledge, and thinking. "Justice” is a sense of humanism, “knowledge” is

the way of humanism, and "thinking" is the triumph of humanism. These concepts turn justice into an irresistible force, being the main weapon of the leader. And an unfair leader will inevitably lose his way.

So, what will be the result, what will be the arrival of a person to the leadership - from among the candidates " who?“, "By what indicators, criteria?“ , "What methods?“, "In what forms?“, "Why choose the same candidate? life itself shows that issues related to determination and intelligent decision-making must be resolved.

What should be the spirituality of a leader? What ideas form the basis of it? Many of the speeches of the President of our country also emphasize these issues. When I agree with people, not to be away from the concerns of the population, live my own misery, and look critically at the work of any Manager, I ask myself whether I meet these requirements, increase my responsibility, fulfill the task assigned to him in a timely manner, and strictly obey the law. This means that in the spiritual leader, first of all, a high sense of responsibility is harmoniously combined with duty and obligation.

Uzbekistan's prospects depend on a number of factors, the first of which is governance institutions. In Uzbekistan, the training and education of modern management personnel is carried out through these management institutions. In Uzbekistan, National governance is based on the principle of commitment to democracy and social justice. Because the state carries out its activities on the basis of the principles of social justice and the rule of law, striving for the well-being of the individual and society.

The greatest criterion for leadership is *fairness*. This word is based on the fate of the entire people, the prospects of society, the fate of our country, which means that justice must be above all else. At the same time, we have no right to remember and fantasize about the fertilizers left to us by our grandfather Emir Temur " In power and justice". Those who are on hand can only tell you about the service, get rid of it. Never forget that a person, as a person, remains, as a citizen, has equal rights with you.

The attitude of ordinary people to the leader creates not only relations between two citizens, but also a spiritual and moral, political and moral environment in which he makes decisions in society. This means that the production culture and its effectiveness directly depend on the mood of people and their attitude to the manager.

A true leader treats everyone equally fairly. Of course, people are different. Among them will be those who do not read sermons, and sometimes profess spirituality. A people is a people with all its qualities, as well as its shortcomings. A true leader, realizing this integrity, feeling it with his mind, bowing his head, following himself, gains worthy respect and glory before the people. For example, one of the Western scientists – Paul Speaker in his work “Social policy: topics and approaches” expresses the opinion that “Social well-being covers all activities, from public social services to social security, agriculture, health care, social work, the education system, hired work, prisons, legal services” [7].

A high level of spirituality, responsibility and culture, which is one of the main criteria, plays an important role in determining the image of a senior employee. This is not only a guarantee of today's global time, but also a factor that determines the essence and meaning of the concept of a leader who can serve and ensure the great future of Uzbekistan.

Society and the nation are free from shortcomings, first of all, from the fact that managers can meet modern requirements, are devoid of moral shortcomings. A modern manager must be a leader, selfless, an example, a model and a model for all the qualities of an employee.

In the Message of the President of our country Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis dated December 22, 2017, it is emphasized that “With the effective implementation of the measures taken in our country, the Executive authorities conduct harmonious activities. Unfortunately, today the level of responsibility in the direction of activity. The fact that the mechanisms of authority are clearly delineated and not defined hinders our work. In this regard, it is necessary to introduce a system of effective decision-making based on openness in public administration. It is advisable to review the principles and mechanisms of interaction between public administration bodies and the Cabinet of Ministers. Each Ministry must ensure the implementation of state policy in the area entrusted to it and bear full responsibility for the final result,” he said. After all, the culture of the leader does not allow you to find the content of such defects. Because the spiritual and moral image of the leader will be embodied in these qualities:

- a person's inability to lead mentally, ethically, and spiritually;
- high spiritual and cultural appearance;
- ability to feel the potential of leadership;
- leadership culture, continuous improvement of their experience and qualifications;
- self-awareness, attitude to history and national values, national pride, pride, devotion to the national idea;
- rely on honesty, justice, legality and reality in public life;
- the ability to apply democratic principles in the management of;
- to harmonize their interests with the interests of the people and society;
- uncompromising struggle against such manifestations as interest in activities, individualism, selflessness, locality;
- creation of a reserve of personnel, their training, retraining and, to be honest, to tell the truth, their placement;
- welfare of the people, happiness of the people, selflessness in the name of the Motherland. Based on these qualities, the image of managers of organizations and enterprises is formed. Let's assume that mastering only one culture of addressing the leader in itself opens the way to gaining people's trust and their penetration into the world of the soul. Only then will the leader be able to fully win the love and trust of people. If, on the contrary, people can not find the strength, then he will lose a large Treasury, in the future such a leader will receive bitter kisses.

President of our country Shavkat Mirziyoyev, harmoniously representing the interests of the people and dialogue with the people, noted that the main priority is "Human interests above all!" the noble idea is that today's leaders should consistently implement it, setting it as a priority.

The first is the introduction of new effective methods and mechanisms for establishing an open dialogue with citizens, including a system of accountability of managers at all levels to the population.

Secondly, to provide for an efficient organization of people's receiving the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and Tashkent city, in every district and city, the Virtual reception of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan is a new, state requirement for managers.

In this regard, the head of our state is obliged to radically change the style and outlook of local khokims and their first deputies. Today, life itself and the demands of the people present us with new and more complex tasks that must be solved in practice.:

First, some departments and their leaders are to a certain extent disconnected from the real life and needs of the people.

Secondly, a superficial approach to the development of concepts and programs for the development of the network and territories is allowed.

And finally, the third main drawback is that most managers are used to solving complex problems without leaving the office, without delving into how things are on the ground.

The manager must have a humane and polite attitude towards ordinary people. This attitude leads to the fact that people freely turn to the manager. As a result, the company will not have any unnecessary problems and misunderstandings, the pace of work will increase, and the atmosphere in the team will become stable. If on the contrary, the manic and arrogant attitude of the manager to the employee indicates his lack of culture. This circumstance in the first place has a negative impact on the most senior staff, as well as the team.

The Executive must be in a state of reasonableness in complex, contentious, and contentious circumstances. Relying on the mind and experience, it eliminates unnecessary actions. The manager should be an example for the team in the employee's ability to behave. Otherwise, the inability of management personnel to behave causes an unfavorable mood in the team and damages the reputation of the leader. After all, these cultural qualities must be consistently assimilated by the manager through life experience.

In accordance with the Strategy for 2017-2021, the three most important requirements for the implementation of the objectives depend on a critical level, says the chief:

The first head of state from the President we're all managers at all levels together, and the result of answer each of us personally.

Second, we must ensure clear order and strict discipline in all areas.

The third is to ensure the cleanliness of our staff, prevent any negative situations at work and dry the roots of such illusions.

The head of our state noted in his regular work that "Our most important task is to strengthen peace and prosperity in the country, to satisfy people and people with life. To do this, our country must first of all agree with the activities of our leaders. To do this, each manager must pull their own cart and be personally responsible for the state of affairs in their area. After that, there will be changes in our society, there will be development"[8], he says. Political scientist N. Juraev said: "The power of the state is seen in raising the standard of living of the population in need of social protection. Already in Uzbekistan, social justice and social protection have become a priority area of state policy"[9].

For any manager working in the management system in the current environment, it is important to know whether he is the leader of any enterprise, organization, community or political figure, to master culture of communication with people, living words to help people explain the policies of the government of Uzbekistan to actively participate in the process of fundamental reforms in our country, and deeply aware of civic duty. The First President of our country, Islam Karimov, is here "...today, a leader must be not only the owner of a certain profession, but also worthy of the people's trust for his activity and humanity, have high

intellectual thinking, be far-sighted, constantly striving for innovation, and eventually like-minded” [10].

This challenge facing our society is to some extent difficult. After all, performing this task requires much more extensive knowledge and thinking in management. In the recent past, it would have been sufficient to apply the method of external coercion during a structure based on repression. Today, people are able to awaken a sense of responsibility for their inner desires, personal decisions. Therefore, it is important that the current leader carefully master the culture of speech and communication, oratory.

In practice, many believe that the effectiveness of management activities of managers largely depends on how long the manager has worked in his post, that is, on the experience gained in the management process. The study indicates that the effectiveness of management activities of managers in organizing and improving the activities of an educational institution largely depends on their understanding, level of knowledge, skills and qualifications of the management direction, as well as on their individual characteristics, professional training and personal qualities.

In the requirements for official duties, special attention is paid to the deep knowledge of managers and teaching staff, first of all, of state policy, regulatory documents in the field of education, rules for organizing the educational process on a scientific basis, and skills for applying them in their activities.

Thus, in accordance with the tasks set by the responsible Ministry of public education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as separate indicators for assessing the level of knowledge, skills and qualifications of heads of educational institutions, the evaluation criteria will pay attention to:

1. Qualification-is a knowledge leader in the field of pedagogy, organization of educational process, knowledge of the participants in the educational process and employees of pedagogical and psychological characteristics, social norms and requirements of profession and specialty, as well as the presence of concepts in the direction of the future specialist and theoretical bases of management of educational institution.

2. Professional skills are based on the existing unified pedagogical requirements, studying the capabilities of teachers and students, taking them into account, forming a school team, coordinating its activities, assisting in solving existing problems and issues when performing tasks facing the team; creating public organizations and involving them in school management; organization of joint activities of teachers and students on the basis of coordinate relations, the coordination of their actions with the need of criticism and self-criticism, discipline and organization; define goals and objectives of management activities; social and psychological skills and skills towards the development of criteria for assessing the performance of teachers and activity teachers.

3. Labor productivity is determined by the effectiveness and quality of indicators of students ' assimilation of state educational standards.

Based on the above information, we can say that managers should be based on innovative approaches to improving the quality of education, have professional personal qualities, self-control in voluntary situations, and also act in accordance with the educational relations prevailing in the educational institution, be guided by existing regulatory criteria in solving

various issues and problems that represent the competence of the head in the direction of management.

In science, the word “dominance” means several. As for the topic of leadership, it means “influencing others”. The expression “impact” in the above meaning means the ability to attract others to yourself through the mind and emotions, to form a sense of kindness towards yourself as a result of interaction. Because the responsibilities and authority of the Manager are not enough for the organization's best practices. According to the experts in the field of management H. Kunz and S. Donnell “If employees worked in accordance with the procedures established by management, they could use 60-65% of their capabilities and fulfill their obligations, justifying their inaction. A manager who intends to make full use of the abilities of employees must be able to awaken a decent feeling in them”[11]. This is where the leader's leadership skills are displayed. In the system of informal relations within the organization, only the leader can fully, that is, 100 percent, involve the abilities of his employees in the work of the team. Another of the qualities inherent in a manager is patience and patience. As you know, a leader works with people with different worldviews. Therefore, in everyday communication with others, it can quickly "infect" negative or positive emotions. Therefore, the leader must be able to resist the influence of others in conflict situations, and to influence difficult ones-with pressure, with a reasonable decision. This quality of personality, on the one hand, is innate, and on the other, depends on life's practical experience. Rational organization of work, that is, pay more attention to the positive aspects of work, wisely eliminate unpleasant situations and be in the circle of closer friends, devote time to physical education and useful activities, helps to improve performance.

Competence in management describes the spiritual outlook of managers, psychological, pedagogical, organizational and technological potential, that is, the potential of their professional capabilities. This potential can be determined by the state and effectiveness of the management process of managers of all educational institutions, starting from pre-school educational institutions, taking into account the specifics of the management process.

The role of public organizations in the development of society and the state is also invaluable. It is through these organizations that progress is being made. “Public and non-governmental organizations that are civil institutions are voluntary associations of people” [12]. This means that the management staff also performs managerial functions there.

This means that the successful completion and effective management process requires the manifestation of certain qualities in the manager himself. At the same time, the moral, psychological and personal qualities shown in the manager guarantee an effective result of management activities. Therefore, heads of educational institutions should also pay attention to the continuous improvement of their spiritual, moral, psychological and personal qualities, and be in demand. Managers who carry out practical actions to improve their moral, psychological and personal qualities will also be able to analyze how effective management activities are in this process.

A smart leader uses moral norms as a basis in the process of organizing collective relationships. And in overcoming the contradictions and conflicts that have arisen, it relies on life experience and spiritual enlightenment, which are crucial. After all, the practical activities and diplomatic relations of the state in the political, social, and economic spheres are based on ethical standards. The higher it is, the more effective the activity, the more it becomes a

determining factor of progress. According to UN expert Keith Griffin, “This system was based on careful and expensive remote (traditional, historical) development that won the trust of local residents” [13].

The activation of globalization processes requires increased attention of the state and leaders of various levels and spheres to the socio-spiritual direction of their activities. At present, patriotism, which is threatened by the threats of globalization, must be managed by the state, supported, and created. Therefore, "...we want to live in harmony with today's life, and not think about the problems and threats that may arise on our way tomorrow, about trade decisions that may fall into our heads. Therefore, a leadership position means service and responsibility to the people”.

However, fair governance is a priority. Because the people conclude that the state, the state system is not fair or unfair, depending on the leader, his activities and attitude to people. When citizens recognize the state as socially just, that is, the system of values and work management adopted by the state will be approved by the majority of society members, patriotism can become a powerful national factor of governance.

President of our country Shavkat Mirziyoyev in relation to today's leaders emphasizes the following: “In order to achieve our goals, we need to organize our work on a new basis, each of us feels deeply responsible and makes every effort in our place. Analytical and critical comments serve as a solid foundation for tomorrow, so that we can master new frontiers.

Today, the time is changing, the demand is growing, and the tasks that we set for ourselves are growing. In such difficult conditions, it is time to work with the mood "You – don't touch me, I-don't touch you”. We are used to looking for an excuse that “the situation is bad, the situation is difficult “ But the question of who will change this situation, who will follow in the footsteps, let's ask ourselves. If we don't change the situation with ourselves, with our own intelligence, with our work, no one from abroad will do it for us” [14].

Indeed, in today's rapidly changing world, the knowledge and experience of national leadership personnel for the development of each nation and state is more relevant and significant than ever, and is a decisive force.

In his speech at the ceremony dedicated to the 29th anniversary of Independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Mirziyoyev said: “Today, when it comes to our country at the world level, the phrase “New Uzbekistan”is pronounced. This is a recognition of the achievements we have made in recent years at a completely new stage of development.

At present, a new foundation of the Renaissance era is being created in Uzbekistan – the third Renaissance, which impresses the majestic strength of our people. Because today's Uzbekistan is not yesterday's Uzbekistan. Today our people are not yesterday's people either “[15].

In fact, we are all equally responsible for the development of the country, our citizens are not spiritually depressed people yesterday. Accordingly, in this life, the state, through its mechanisms, develops reforms to achieve its goals and identifies individuals who guide these reforms as leaders.

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